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Efficient Damage Simulation Method for Textile Composite Using Fiber-bundles / Matrix-resin Separated Model

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Woven composites, Textile CFRP

Example of tow structure

- ✓ Reinforced by mesoscopic carbon fiber tow structure
- ✓ **Higher strength and toughness in the out-of-plane direction**

- Complex geometry of meso-scale structure
- Complex damage process of textile composite
- **Analysis of damage evolution and its effect by using numerical simulation is necessary.**

Progressive damage analysis based on finite element method

Issues in the finite element analysis of textile composites

- **Huge effort** is needed for **mesh generation**.
- **Distorted elements** are often generated.

Degraded calculation accuracy
Increased calculation cost

Separated mesh approach

Fiber bundle and matrix resin are *separately meshed*

Fiber bundle mesh

+

Matrix resin mesh

- ✓ **Less effort for mesh generation**
- ✓ **No distorted small resin elements**

Goal of this study

Propose a finite element modeling method for textile composite, in which **fiber bundle and matrix resin are *separately meshed***

1. Formulation
2. Validation
3. Progressive damage analysis of textile composite
4. Summary

1. Formulation

2. Validation

3. Progressive damage analysis of textile composite

4. Summary

Connection between two separated subdomains

Overlap of domains

Unmatched interface to be connected

Matrix resin subdomain Fiber bundle subdomain Analytical domain

Proposed method

Usual FEM

Fiber bundle elements **partially overlap** matrix resin elements

- ✓ **Simple regular mesh** is used for resin subdomain. **No distorted element** exists.
- ✓ Mesh overlap is allowed.

Bilinear cohesive zone model

- Fiber bundle elements and matrix resin elements are **connected by bilinear cohesive zone model**

Procedure of user subroutine UEL

- ① Calculate stiffness matrix of cut resin element K_{sol}
An element is divided into subcells, **the stiffnesses of non-overlapped subcells** are integrated.
- ② Calculate traction t , and interface stiffness K_{coh} using separated bundle and resin meshes.
Displacement jump δ is calculated at **evaluation points (Δ) distributed on the interface.**
- ③ Total stiffness matrix ($K_{sol} + K_{coh}$) is calculated, and overall equation is solved by **ABAQUS**.

Rectangle grid mesh
allows fast calculation

1. Formulation

2. Validation

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4. Summary

Simulation of cylindrical inclusion (carbon fiber) embedded in the matrix resin

Mesh used for proposed method

Elastic moduli of T700S

$$E_L = 177.9 \text{ GPa} \quad E_T = 26.1 \text{ GPa}$$

$$\nu_{LT} = 0.27 \quad G_{LT} = 23.9 \text{ GPa}$$

$$\nu_{TT} = 0.77$$

Elastic moduli of epoxy matrix

$$E = 2.86 \text{ GPa} \quad \nu = 0.36$$

**Mesh for reference calculation
(Conventional method)**

Parameters of cohesive region

$$G_{IC} = G_{IIC} = 0.10 \text{ kJ/m}^2$$

$$K_{ini} = 1.0 \times 10^7 \text{ GPa/m}$$

$$t_I = t_{II} = 78.0 \text{ MPa}$$

Boundary condition

3% tensile strain is applied by displacement

Validation results

Strain $\epsilon_x^G = 1.2\%$

Strain along the path P1-P2 ($\epsilon_x^G = 2.4\%$)

Strain $\epsilon_x^G = 2.4\%$

Proposed method achieves precise simulation of damage propagation.

1. Formulation

2. Validation

3. Progressive damage analysis of textile composite

4. Summary

Mesh used for proposed method

Matrix resin mesh
(Cuboid grid mesh)

Fiber bundle mesh

+

Mesh generation procedure

- ① Prepare fiber bundle mesh and simple cuboid grid mesh.
- ② Bore the matrix mesh
 - Delete matrix elements fully overlapped by the fiber bundle elements
- ③ Two meshes are connected by the proposed method

Resin mesh generation is very easy and only takes short time.

✓ Tetrahedral elements are used for matrix region

Mesh for conventional method

96,247 resin nodes
194,473 fiber bundle nodes

Elastic moduli of fiber bundle

$E_L = 143.9 \text{ GPa}$	$E_T = 8.88 \text{ GPa}$
$\nu_{LT} = 0.304$	$G_{LT} = 4.5 \text{ GPa}$
$\nu_{TT} = 0.452$	

Elastic moduli of epoxy

$E = 3.10 \text{ GPa}$	$\nu = 0.438$
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Mesh for proposed method

50% reduced resin nodes
17% reduced in full model

48,464 resin nodes
194,473 fiber bundle nodes

Parameters of cohesive zone model

$G_{IC} = 0.277 \text{ kJ/m}^2$	$G_{IIC} = 0.788 \text{ kJ/m}^2$
$K_{ini} = 8.0 \times 10^6 \text{ GPa/m}$	
$t_{I} = 69.0 \text{ MPa}$	$t_{II} = 100.0 \text{ MPa}$

Boundary condition

1% tensile strain is applied by displacement

σ_x distribution (central weft bundles)

$\varepsilon_G = 0.60\%$

Proposed method

Conventional method

- ✓ Overall stress distribution agrees well in both model
- ✓ Position and strain of occurrence of debonding agree well
- ✓ Delamination propagation behavior agrees well

σ_x distribution (central weft bundles)

$$\varepsilon_G = 0.65\%$$

Proposed method

Conventional method

- ✓ Overall stress distribution agrees well in both model
- ✓ Position and strain of occurrence of debonding agree well
- ✓ Delamination propagation behavior agrees well

σ_x distribution (central weft bundles)

$\varepsilon_G = 1.00\%$

Proposed method

Conventional method

S, S11 (CSYS-1)
(平均: 75%)

- ✓ Overall stress distribution agrees well in both model
- ✓ Position and strain of occurrence of debonding agree well
- ✓ Delamination propagation behavior agrees well

- A new finite element modeling method for progressive damage analysis of textile composite was proposed, in which **fiber bundle and matrix resin are separately meshed**, and they are connected by using cohesive zone model.
- Validity of the proposed method was demonstrated by comparing the results to the conventional FEM results.
- **Mesh generation is very easy and takes short time**. Textile geometries can be modeled much smaller number of the nodes and elements.
- The proposed method can achieve precise damage progressive simulation of textile composites.